

8T – Dark Energy and Outer Manifold Shells

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, in particular the varying (3,1) Lorentz manifolds, it is possible to expand the idea of dark energy as described by the main equation to outer-shells of the manifold interacting. Such an idea is easier to visualize. The extremum curvatures of distinct manifolds is taking place in the outer-shell of the matrix tensor.

Introduction

The new 8T framework is revolving around a variational Lorentz manifolds, which assumed stationary. Using the main equation of the theory and the two conditions specified in equations (1.1) it is possible to describe the so-called "dark energy". The reason for this can be derived from a variation of equation one, by assuming that there are infinite amount of manifolds all demanded to be stationary, that is described by equation (1.1)

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad , \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

However, given that representation of the main equation we are facing with an interesting question. Suppose that there are in fact infinite number of manifolds wrapping one another, why are they not visible to us? That is the point of this short essay. Each manifold is interacting with other manifold in the outer shell of the manifold itself. This outer shell is the result of areas of maximal curvature on each manifold. The result of this interaction is synonymous with the time invariant acceleration.

In contrast to GR, the areas of Extremum curvatures is due to bosonic ripple fields propagating from matter clusters. The ripple fields are isomorphic to prime numbers or one. That is the idea which yielded the celebrated series of coupling constants, as you probably know by now. While Einstein theory refers to fermion clusters as the source of matrix tensor curvatures. That is not accurate as Einstein does not take the effect of spin two.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.3}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.31}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.32}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

The curvature is due to the cluster of galaxies, i.e. cluster of arbitrary variations on each matrix tensor. These retain their form by the coupling constants series and the demand we imposed on equation (1), what is varying is the area in between each of them, that is due to an area of maximal curvature on distinct manifold. The main point of this paper and the innovative part is that each manifold has an outer shell not directly visible to the residents of the manifold itself. According to this explanation we can reason the dark part of the dark energy. The hyperbole external part of the line is representing the other-shell of the manifold.

Another mathematical representation of dark energy is by summing the direct product of infinite manifolds interacting with each other causing the metric tensor between each manifold to accelerate outward while preserving the areas of extremum curvature on each manifold, than is given in equation (1.4).

$$S_1 \ominus \left(\sum_{i=1}^N S_i \right) = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

$$S_i \cap S_1 \in (M, g) \cap (3,1)$$

The multiverse is really a sphere packing structure, and the distance in between each area of extremum curvature if one analysis and intuition are correct are appearing in the outer shell of the manifold. If so, so does the so-called dark energy.

References

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